

Nutrients Enhancement and Organoleptic Properties of Cheese-Like Products from Cashew Nuts (*Anacardium Occidentale*) Spiced with Alligator Pepper, Garlic and Ginger

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Abstract

Spices are known for their health benefits and thus, commonly used in foods to enhance taste, flavour and shelf life. This study produced cheese-like product spiced with medicinal spices (alligator pepper, garlic and ginger), assessed their nutrient contents and organoleptic properties using standard methods. The result of the proximate showed an increase in the protein (10.80 - 14.05%), fibre (13.95 -19.05%), ash (2.75 -3.80%), and carbohydrate content (23.50 - 37.50%), of the cheese-like product with an increment in the medicinal spices. Cashew nut cheese spiced with 3 g of alligator pepper exhibited the high antioxidant properties with OH (67.20 mg/ml) being the highest followed by DPPH (51.90 mg/100 g) and phenolic content (27.96 mg GAE/g). Inclusion of 3 g of the spices to cheese like product gain wide acceptance by consumers due to savory. Spices can be successfully supplemented into cheese products to enhance their nutrients and to alleviate the intolerance of individual that are allergic to dairy products.

Keywords: cashew nuts, cheese like -product, alligator pepper, garlic and ginger

INTRODUCTION

Cheese is a widely consumed dairy product known for its high nutritional value, particularly its richness in protein, calcium, and essential fatty acids (Oladipo *et al.*, 2020). However, the increasing prevalence of lactose intolerance has led to a growing demand for plant-based cheese alternatives. This challenge has stimulated interest in non-dairy cheese products derived from locally available plant sources in Nigeria, such as cashew nuts (*Anacardium occidentale*) (Oyeyinka *et al.*, 2019). Cashew nuts are rich in essential nutrients, including unsaturated fats, proteins, and antioxidants, making them a suitable base material for cheese analogs (Ajibola *et al.*, 2018). In addition, cashew nuts are abundantly cultivated in Nigeria, providing an affordable and sustainable raw material for plant-based food innovation (Oyeyinka *et al.*, 2019). Alligator pepper (*Aframomum melegueta*), a spice widely used in West African cuisine and traditional medicine, is valued not only for its distinctive flavor but also for its antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (Akinwande *et al.*, 2017). Garlic (*Allium sativum*) is another versatile spice known for its pungent flavor and numerous health-promoting properties. It contains bioactive compounds that provide antioxidant benefits, support cardiovascular health, and exhibit antibacterial and

antiviral activities (Sobolewska, 2019). Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), another readily available Nigerian crop, contains bioactive compounds such as gingerols and shogaols, which possess potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Arogundade *et al.*, 2023). Incorporating these medicinal spices (alligator pepper, garlic and ginger) plant-based cheese products may not only enhance their functional health benefits but also allow evaluation of the synergistic effects of these spices on the antioxidant and organoleptic properties of cashew-based cheese analogs. This formulation could further establish their potential as lactose-free alternatives to conventional dairy cheese, thereby addressing lactose intolerance and promoting the consumption of nutritionally enriched, plant-based foods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Souring of materials

Cashew nuts, fresh alligator pepper, garlic and ginger rhizomes were procured from Okitipupa market, Ondo State, Nigeria. All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade.

Processing of spice powder

Fresh alligator pepper, garlic and ginger were processed into powder according to the method described by Fatureti and Ogidi (2025). The spices were sorted, cleaned and oven dried at 50 °C for 6 h. Dried spices were pulverized into fine powder using kitchen electric grinder (70–300 mesh, Raylux, China) and stored in air tight container.

Production of spiced cheese-like products from cashew nuts

Spiced cheese - like products were produced according to the methods described by Oyeyinka *et al.* (2019) with slight modification. Approximately 1000 g of roasted cashew nuts were weighed and thoroughly washed to remove debris and impurities. The nuts were soaked in 800 ml of water for 1 h to soften, then rinsed, decanted, and drained. The softened nuts were blended with 120 ml of water to obtain a smooth paste, which was weighed and divided into four portions: one control and three with 1 g, 2 g, and 3 g of added spices (alligator pepper, garlic and ginger) respectively. Each portion received 2 ml of lime juice to aid coagulation, mixed thoroughly, covered with aluminum foil, and sealed with paper tape. Samples were pasteurized in a water bath at 80 °C for 30 min until a clean break was observed. After cooling to 37 - 42 °C, 1 g starter culture was added per sample and allowed for 1 h to ferment. Fermentation was halted by reheating the samples at 80 °C for 15 min. The cooled curds were then cut into small cubes to form spiced cashew cheese-products.

Determination of proximate composition spiced cheese-like products from cashew nuts

The proximate composition of spiced cheese-like product samples was assessed using the standard procedures specified by AOAC (2015) method. Moisture content was determined by oven drying at 105 °C. Crude fibre by gravimetric method. Crude fat content was determined via the solvent extraction method with n-hexane. Crude protein content was evaluated via the Kjeldahl apparatus for nitrogen (N) and the crude protein content was calculated by multiplying the nitrogen value (N) by a factor of 6.25. Ash content was determined by dry ashing in a muffle furnace at 555 °C, while the carbohydrate content was determined by difference

Determination of antioxidant properties spiced cheese-like products from cashew nuts

The extraction technique was used to collect supernatant from 1 g of spiced cheese-like products samples using the rotary shaker (Centurium Scientific, United Kingdom) at 190 rpm-220 rpm for 3 h, filtered, and centrifuged (Centurium Scientific, United Kingdom) at 5000 rpm for 15 mins. The total phenolic content of the sample extracts was quantified using Folin–Ciocalteu method by El-Aziz *et al.* (2010). [Gallic acid was used as a standard for comparison and the results are expressed in milligrams of Gallic Acid Equivalent per 100 g sample (mg GAE/100 g).

Concentrated methanolic extracts was used for the estimation of total flavonoid and the absorbance was read at 510 nm (Tiara *et al.*, 2021). Different aliquots of known concentration of rutin were treated as standard and the results are expressed as mg of Rutin Equivalent per 100 g sample (mg RE/100 g). The DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging activity of the samples was determined using the method of by Dissanayake *et al.* (2020). Total antioxidant capacity using FRAP assay was determined according to Brand-Williams *et al.* (1995). Trolox (water-soluble vitamin E analogue) was used as standard for the comparison and results are expressed as mg Trolox Equivalent per 100 g sample (mg TE/100 g). The ABTS [2,2'-Azino-bis (3-ethyl benzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt] radical scavenging activity assay was carried out using the modified auto-bleaching method as outlined by Re *et al.* (1999).

Determination of antioxidant properties spiced cheese-like products from cashew nuts

Organoleptic properties were carried out by trained thirty panelists on the spiced cheese-like products from cashew nuts as described by Bamigboye *et al.* (2022). The judges scored the samples for colour, taste (sweet, bitter, sour and salty), texture, characteristics flavour and overall acceptability using a 9-point hedonic scale ranging from 1 = dislike extremely and 9 = like extremely.

Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate. The data were analyzed using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), followed by Duncan's multiple range test to determine significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate composition of the spiced cheese-like products is presented in Table 1. The moisture content of the non-spiced cheese-like product was the highest ($p \leq 0.05$) at 39.85%. High moisture content in food products promotes the growth of bacteria, yeasts, and molds, thereby predisposing them to early spoilage. Faturoti and Ogidi (2025) reported that foods with high moisture content are more susceptible to microbial invasion over time if not properly stored. The inclusion of medicinal spices in the cheese significantly reduced the moisture content, with values ranging from 20.95% to 30.20%. The lower moisture content of the spiced cheese-like products suggests reduced water activity, which may inhibit the growth of spoilage microorganisms. The protein content of the spiced cheese-like products (10.80–14.05%) was higher than that of the control. This agrees with the findings of Adedeji *et al.* (2020), who reported increased protein content in cheese produced from soy and coconut milk using selected coagulants. The observed increase in protein content may be attributed to the high protein composition of cashew nuts (Olatidoye *et al.*, 2020). This indicates that incorporation spices into cheese-like products make the protein available for consumers. Protein is an essential macronutrient required for tissue repair, muscle growth, and various metabolic functions (Faturoti and Ogidi, 2025). Table 2 presents the antioxidant properties of the spiced cheese-like products. The inclusion of alligator pepper, garlic, and ginger enhanced antioxidant activity, particularly in DPPH radical scavenging (36.60–57.90%) and hydroxyl radical inhibition (42.05–64.60 mg/mL). This demonstrates strong antioxidant potential, indicating that the spiced cheese-like products possess high free radical-trapping capacity. The enhanced antioxidant properties suggest that spice supplementation could play a vital role in mitigating oxidative stress, which is associated with chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disorders and cancer (Adedeji *et al.*, 2013; Alieozaman *et al.*, 2024). The organoleptic properties of the spiced cheese-like products are presented in Table 3. The result indicated that all samples were well accepted by the panelists.

This aligns with the findings of Hammam *et al.* (2019), who reported that spices improve the sensory attributes of food, thereby increasing consumer acceptability. The addition of spices enhanced color, aroma, taste, and flavor, making the cheese-like products more appealing and suitable for consumption, particularly by individuals with lactose intolerance.

Table 1. Proximate Composition of Spiced Cheese Like-Product from Cashew Nut

Samples	Moisture (%)	Protein (%)	Crude Fibre (%)	Fat (%)	Ash (%)	CHO (%)
CNAGG	39.85 ± 0.25 ^a 23.95±0.15 ^b	10.80±1.00 ^e 12.00±0.20 ^c	13.95 ± 0.15 ^f 17.30±0.20 ^c	9.15 ± 0.25 ^a 6.40±0.10 ^b	2.75 ± 0.05 ^d 3.55±0.05 ^b	23.50± 0.70 ^d 36.80±0.20 ^a
CNAPA	21.90±0.10 ^c	13.35±0.45 ^b	18.00±0.10 ^b	6.15±0.05 ^{bc}	3.70±0.10 ^a	36.90 ±0.60 ^a
CNAPB	20.95±0.15 ^d	14.05±0.25 ^a	19.05±0.25 ^a	5.95±0.15 ^c	3.80±0.10 ^a	36.20±0.90 ^a
CNAPC	30.20±0.85 ^b	11.25±0.07 ^d	15.85±0.07 ^e	7.65±0.07 ^b	3.05±0.07 ^c	32.00±0.99 ^c
CNGAA	27.30±0.57 ^c	11.25±0.21 ^d	16.05±0.21 ^d	7.60±0.14 ^b	3.15±0.07 ^b	34.65±0.07 ^b
CNGAB	24.15±0.78 ^d	11.30±0.00 ^d	16.55±0.07 ^d	7.15±0.07 ^b	3.35±0.07 ^b	37.50±0.85 ^a
CNGAC						
CNG1A	27.30 ± 0.50 ^b	11.5 ± 0.35 ^d	18.15 ± 0.65 ^b	7.25 ± 0.15 ^b	3.05 ± 0.05 ^c	32.70± 0.30 ^c
CNG1B	24.25 ± 0.35 ^c	11.35±0.25 ^d	18.75 ± 0.35 ^b	7.35 ± 0.05 ^b	3.40 ± 0.10 ^b	34.90± 0.90 ^b
CNG1C	22.60 ±0.010 ^d	11.55±0.35 ^d	19.55 ± 0.05 ^a	7.05 ± 0.15 ^b	3.60 ± 0.10 ^a	35.65± 0.05 ^b

Mean ± SD with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at P < 0.05. (n = 4). CNAGG- cheese without spice, CNAPA-99 g cashew paste with 1 g alligator pepper, CNAPB- 98 g cashew paste with 2 g alligator pepper, CNAPC- 97 g cashew paste cheese with 3 g alligator pepper, CNGAA- 99 g cashew paste with 1 g garlic, CNGAB- 98 g cashew paste with 2% garlic, CNGAC- 97 g cashew paste with 3 g garlic paste, CNG1A – 99 g cashew paste with 1 g ginger, CNG1B- 98 g cashew paste with 2 g ginger, CNG1C- 97 g cashew paste with 3 g ginger

Table 2. Antioxidant Properties of Spiced Cheese Like-Products from Cashew Nut

Samples	Phenolic (mg RE/ g)	Flavonoid (mg GAE/ g)	OH (mg/ml)	FRAP (mg/ml)	ABTS (mg/ml)	DPPH (%)
CNAGG	14.18±0.68 ^d 19.29±0.57 ^{ab}	6.15±0.25 ^d 7.82±0.10 ^c	42.05±0.21 ^d 55.25±0.63 ^c	8.30±0.04 ^d 11.78±0.14 ^c	0.77±0.01 ^d 1.12±0.00 ^c	36.60±0.70 ^d 43.30±0.20 ^c
CNAPA	20.35±0.07 ^{ab}	8.89±0.04 ^b	58.80±0.99 ^b	13.53±0.02 ^b	1.13±0.00 ^b	47.60 ±0.60 ^b
CNAPB	21.91±0.16 ^a	9.27±0.06 ^a	64.60±0.71 ^a	14.05±0.11 ^a	1.14±0.00 ^a	57.90±0.90 ^a
CNAPC	16.01±0.80 ^c	7.23±0.25 ^c	50.05±1.25 ^c	12.29±0.01 ^c	1.13±0.00 ^c	39.40±0.99 ^c
CNGAA	19.01±0.11 ^b	8.14±0.20 ^b	54.35±0.75 ^b	13.60±0.43 ^b	1.21±0.00 ^b	41.50±0.07 ^b
CNGAB	19.96±0.06 ^a	8.91±0.12 ^a	57.95±0.25 ^a	15.19±0.32 ^a	1.34±0.00 ^a	43.90±0.85 ^a
CNGAC	21.85 ± 0.19 ^c	9.70 ± 0.06 ^c	58.05 ± 0.25 ^c	16.15 ± 0.25 ^c	0.91 ± 0.00 ^c	42.20± 0.30 ^c
CNG1A	23.92 ± 0.18 ^b	11.90 ± 0.60 ^b	62.90 ± 0.20 ^b	17.40 ± 0.00 ^b	1.00 ± 0.00 ^b	43.90± 0.90 ^b
CNG1B	27.96 ± 0.95 ^a	14.78 ± 0.41 ^a	67.20 ± 0.40 ^a	18.70 ± 0.40 ^a	1.01 ± 0.00 ^a	46.90± 0.05 ^a
CNG1C						

Mean ± SD with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at P < 0.05. (n = 4). CNAGG- cheese without spice, CNAPA-99 g cashew paste with 1 g alligator pepper, CNAPB- 98 g cashew paste with 2 g alligator pepper, CNAPC- 97 g cashew paste cheese with 3 g alligator pepper, CNGAA- 99 g cashew paste with 1 g garlic, CNGAB- 98 g cashew paste with 2% garlic, CNGAC- 97 g cashew paste with 3 g garlic paste, CNGIA – 99 g cashew paste with 1 g ginger, CNG1B- 98 g cashew paste with 2 g ginger, CNG1C- 97 g cashew paste with 3 g ginger

Table 3. Organoleptic Properties of Spiced Cheese – like Products from Cashew Nut

Mean \pm SD with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at $P < 0.05$. CNAGG- cheese without spice, CNAPA-99 g cashew paste with 1 g alligator pepper, CNAPB- 98 g cashew paste with 2 g alligator pepper, CNAPC- 97 g cashew paste cheese with 3 g alligator pepper, CNGAA- 99 g cashew paste with 1 g garlic, CNGAB- 98 g cashew paste with 2% garlic, CNGAC- 97 g cashew paste with 3 g garlic paste, CNGIA – 99 g cashew paste

Samples	Colour	Taste	Aroma	Texture	Mouthfeel	Characteristic flavour	General acceptability
CNAGG	7.20 \pm 0.89 ^a	7.10 \pm 0.85 ^a	7.60 \pm 0.68 ^a	6.80 \pm 1.10 ^a	6.55 \pm 0.60 ^a	6.65 \pm 0.87 ^a	6.60 \pm 0.75 ^a
CNAPA	7.30 \pm 1.42 ^a	6.35 \pm 1.73 ^a	6.80 \pm 1.06 ^a	7.00 \pm 1.25 ^{ab}	6.95 \pm 1.76 ^a	6.60 \pm 1.77 ^a	6.95 \pm 1.61 ^a
CNAPB	6.81 \pm 1.72 ^a	6.31 \pm 1.58 ^a	6.63 \pm 1.02 ^a	6.69 \pm 1.25 ^a	6.62 \pm 1.45 ^a	6.43 \pm 1.82 ^a	6.88 \pm 1.20 ^a
CNAPC	6.85 \pm 1.42 ^a	6.55 \pm 1.23 ^a	6.90 \pm 1.25 ^a	6.25 \pm 1.65 ^a	6.70 \pm 1.17 ^a	7.15 \pm 1.18 ^a	6.80 \pm 1.24 ^a
CNGAA	6.80 \pm 1.24 ^a	6.60 \pm 1.19 ^a	6.55 \pm 1.32 ^a	6.35 \pm 1.32 ^a	6.35 \pm 1.53 ^a	6.50 \pm 1.54 ^a	6.50 \pm 1.15 ^a
CNGAB	7.20 \pm 1.20 ^a	6.20 \pm 0.94 ^a	6.40 \pm 1.31 ^a	6.55 \pm 1.15 ^a	6.00 \pm 1.30 ^a	6.10 \pm 1.89 ^a	6.10 \pm 1.45 ^a
CNGAC	6.90 \pm 1.07 ^a	6.50 \pm 1.94 ^a	6.50 \pm 1.19 ^a	6.75 \pm 1.41 ^a	6.50 \pm 1.35 ^a	6.70 \pm 1.50 ^a	6.80 \pm 1.28 ^a
CNGIA	7.10 \pm 0.71 ^a	6.75 \pm 0.85 ^b	6.10 \pm 0.91 ^c	6.30 \pm 1.12 ^a	6.55 \pm 0.88 ^a	6.05 \pm 1.23 ^a	5.95 \pm 0.82 ^b
CNGIB	7.00 \pm 1.02 ^a	7.50 \pm 0.94 ^a	7.05 \pm 1.27 ^a	6.50 \pm 0.88 ^a	6.40 \pm 0.88 ^a	6.20 \pm 1.00 ^a	6.35 \pm 0.93 ^a
CNGIC	7.05 \pm 0.88 ^a	7.65 \pm 1.03 ^a	6.70 \pm 0.97 ^b	5.60 \pm 1.56 ^b	6.15 \pm 1.03 ^a	6.20 \pm 1.00 ^a	6.30 \pm 1.08 ^a

with 1 g ginger, CNG1B- 98 g cashew paste with 2 g ginger, CNG1C- 97 g cashew paste with 3 g ginger

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study has shown that inclusion of medicinal spices in cheese-like products made from cashew nuts enhances their nutrient contents. This suggests that the products may offer therapeutic benefits and helps boost immunity. Furthermore, the spiced - cheese like products were well accepted by the organoleptic panelist and can serve as a suitable alternative to animal-based cheese, particularly for individuals with lactose intolerance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Clinical or dietary trials should be carried out to validate the potential therapeutic effects of spiced cheese-like products, particularly their impact on immune function, lipid profiles and oxidative stress biomarkers. Furthermore, to ensure safety and marketability, future research should assess the shelf life and microbiological stability of the spiced cheese-like products under various storage conditions.

REFERENCES

- Adedeji, T.O., Oluwalana, I.B. and Ade-Omowaye, B. I. O. (2013). Investigation on antioxidant and anti-nutritional properties of sorghum stem sheath-ginger extract based non-alcoholic beverage. *International Journal of Food Science and Nutrition Engineering*, 3(3):28-34.
- Ajibola, C. F., Malomo, S. A., and Fagbemi, T. N. (2018). Nutritional and functional properties of cashew nut-based cheese analogue. *Nigerian Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 36(1):34–40.
- Akinwande, B. A., Adeoti, O. I. and Ogunleye, A. S. (2017). Effect of *Aframomum melegueta* on the sensory properties of dairy products. *Nigerian Journal of Nutritional Sciences*, 38 (1):72-79.
- Alieozaman, Md S., Chwdhury, M., Fatima, A. and Dev, M. (2024). An overview of spices and herbs as natural antioxidant sources. *Journal of Current Research in Food Science*, 5:31-35.
- AOAC. (2015). Association of official analytical chemists. official methods of analysis. 15th, Washington D.C. USA: Oxford university press, Vol. 2 pp. 910–928.
- Ayodeji, A. A, Ahure, D, Efiong, E. E, and Acham, I. O. (2020). Production and quality evaluation of cheese from soy and coconut milk using selected coagulants. *European Journal of Nutrition & Food Safety*. 12(7): 1-12.
- Bamigboye, C. A., Alake, O. O. and Aderibigbe, A. F. (2022). Effect of ginger and garlic on shelf-life and sensory quality of yoghurt from tiger nut milk. *Nigerian Food Journal*, 40(2): 23–30.
- Brand-Williams, W., Cuvelier, M.E. and Berset, C. (1995). Use of a free radical method to evaluate antioxidant activity, *LWT Food Sci. Technol.* 28 25–30.
- Dissanayake, K. G. C., Liyanage, R., and Waliwita, W. A. L. (2020). A review on medicinal uses of *Zingiber officinale* (ginger). *International Journal of Health Sciences Research*, 10(6):142–148.
- El-Aziz, M. A., Faten, L. S., Sahar, H. S. M., and Hayam, M. A. (2010). Properties of functional soft cheese fortified with ginger extract. *Journal of Food and Dairy Science*, 1(7):429–439.
- Faturoti, A.O. and Ogidi, C.O. (2025). Inclusion of antimicrobial and antioxidant spices into milk candy towards enhancement of nutrient contents and bio-functional activities. *Heliyon*, 11: e42249.
- Hammam, A. R., & Ahmed, E. M. (2019). Garlic supplementation in plant-based foods: Antioxidant capacity and sensory attributes. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 43(12), 1438-1445.
- Oladipo, I. C., Durojaiye, M. O. and Ayoola, T. O. (2020). Microbial quality and nutritional composition of cheese analogues from soy and coconut milk. *African Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 11(5):112–118.
- Olatidoye, O.P., Shittu, T.A., Awonorin, S.O. and Ajisegiri, E.S.A. (2020). Nutritional profile, protein quality, biological value of raw and roasted cashew kernels (*Anacardium occidentale*) grown in southwest Nigeria. *Croatian Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 12(1).

- Oyeyinka, A. T., Odukoya, J. O. and Adebayo, Y. S. (2019). Nutritional composition and consumer acceptability of cheese analog from soy and cashew nut milk. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 43(9):e14285. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.14285>.
- Re, R., Pellegrini, N., Proteggente, A., Pannala, A., Yang, M. and Rice-Evans, C.A. (1999). Antioxidant activity applying an improved ABTS radical cation decolorization assay, *Free Rad. Biol. Med.* 26 1231–1237.
- Sobolewska, D. and Podolak, I. (2019). Bioactive compounds in garlic and their health benefits. *Molecules*, 24(9), 1715.
- Tiara, A., Zakariyah, A., and Adeyemo, F. (2021). Effect of ginger paste on plant-based cheese. *Journal of Food Process Engineering*, 44(1):e13562.